

MPowerBIO

Empowering SME Clusters to help SMEs to overcome the valley of death

Deliverable 2.4 MPowerBIO Digital Toolbox

Document ID	D2.4
Due date	31/01/2021
Delivery date	31/01/2021
Dissemination level	Public
Document version	1.0

Partners

This project has received funding from the Bio-Based Industries Joint Undertaking under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 887501.

DOCUMENT INFORMATION	
Acronym	MPowerBIO
Title	Empowering SME Clusters to help SMEs overcome the valley of death
Grant Number	Agreement 887501
Call	H2020-BBI-JTI-2019
Project Coordinator	Food & Bio Cluster Denmark (FBCD)
Work Package	WP2 Set up and Maintain the Online Tools Supporting MPowerBIO
Lead beneficiary	Tech Tour Global

AUTHOR(S) AND CONTRIBUTORS	
Name	Organisation
Milena Garthley, Daniela Krasteva, Youssef Sabbah	Tech Tour Global
Britt Sandvad	Food & Bio Cluster Denmark

PEER REVIEWERS		
	Date	Name
WP leader	28/01/2021	Milena Garthley
Approval Coordinator	29/10/2021	Britt Sandvad

DOCUMENT HISTORY			
Version	Date	Modifications	Author
0.1	26.01.2021	Initial content	Daniela Krasteva
0.2	27/01/2021	Feedback from consortium partners	Daniela Krasteva
1.0	29/01/2021	Final version	Britt Sandvad

MPOWERBIO PARTNERS				
Participant No	Participant organisation name	Short name	Country	Organisation type
1	Food & Bio Cluster Denmark http://foodbiocluster.dk/	FBCD	DK	Non-profit SME/Cluster
2	Tech Tour Global https://www.techtour.com/	TTG	BG	SME
3	CLIB https://www.clib2021.de/	CLIB	DE	Non-profit SME/Cluster
4	Corporacion Tecnologica de Andalucia https://www.corporaciontecnologica.com/es/	CTA	ES	Non-profit Research Centre/Cluster
5	Italbiotec https://www.italbiotec.it/	IBT	IT	Non-profit Research Centre/Cluster
6	FoodScale Hub https://foodscaleshub.com/	FSH	RS	Non-profit Association /Cluster
7	EIT Food https://www.eitfood.eu/	EIT	BE	Non-profit Association
8	Irish Bioeconomy Foundation https://bioeconomyfoundation.com/	IBF	IE	Non-profit SME/Cluster
9	Q-Plan International https://qplan-intl.gr/	QPL	GR	SME
10	Sustainable Innovations Europe https://www.sustainableinnovations.eu/	SIE	ES	SME

Table of Contents

List of abbreviations	6
Introduction	7
Executive Summary	8
1. Main characteristics of the MPowerBIO digital tools.....	9
1.1 Operational procedures	9
1.2 Technologies used for creation of the platform.....	9
1.3 Resources	10
1.4 Privacy policy.....	10
2. Main Pages of the MPowerBIO website	11
2.1 Site map	11
2.2 Website structure.....	11
3. Application and assessment tool.....	20
3.1 Cluster Application.....	20
3.2 SMEs Application.....	21
3.3 SMEs Self-assessment of Investment Readiness Level.....	27
3.4 Assessment by experts.....	33
3.3. Generating a Service Action Plan	36
4. E-learning tool.....	37
5. Future steps.....	37

List of Figures and Tables

Figure 1-MPowerBIO Platform architecture	10
Figure 2-MPowerBIO website map.....	11
Figure 3-Front page part one	12
Figure 4-Front page part two.....	13
Figure 5-Front page part three	13
Figure 6-Front page part four.....	14
Figure 7-Front page part five.....	14
Figure 8-About view page part one.....	15
Figure 9-About view page part two.....	15
Figure 10-About view page part three	16
Figure 11-About view page part four	17
Figure 12-Services page part one	17
Figure 13-Services page part two	18
Figure 14-Services page part three.....	18
Figure 15-News page	19
Figure 16-Contact page	19
Figure 17-Cluster application page part one.....	21
Figure 18-Application page part one	22
Figure 19-Application page part two	22
Figure 20-Application page part three.....	23
Figure 21-Application page part four.....	24
Figure 22-Application page part six.....	25
Figure 23-Application page part seven	25
Figure 24-Application page part eight	26
Figure 25-Application page part nine	27
Figure 26-Self-Assessment part one	29
Figure 27-Self-Assessment part two	30
Figure 28-Self-Assessment part three.....	30
Figure 29-Self-Assessment part four.....	31
Figure 30-Self-Assessment part five	31
Figure 31-Self-Assessment part six.....	32
Figure 32-Self-Assessment part seven	32
Figure 33-Expert Assessment part one.....	33
Figure 34-Expert Assessment part two	34
Figure 35-Expert Assessment part three.....	35
Figure 36-Expert Assessment part four	36
Figure 37-Generating a Service Action Plan	37

List of abbreviations

CEO	Chief Executive Officer
FAQ	Frequently Asked Questions
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IRL	Investment Readiness Level
IT	Information Technology
KPI	Key Project Indicator
SME	Small or Medium-Sized Enterprise
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats
WP	Work Package

Introduction

This document describes the MPowerBIO platform which is prepared in the context of Work Package 2 (Set up and maintain the online tools supporting MPowerBIO), namely Task 2.1 (Set up the platform to facilitate the project processes) and Task 2.2. Set up the e-learning platform that will host the online courses. MPowerBIO aims at empowering SME Clusters to help SMEs to Overcome the Financial Valley of Death. It will empower 90 clusters within the bio-based industry across Europe to be better equipped to help 250 SMEs overcome the challenge of finding investment to get from idea to business and get one step closer to capturing investment.

The MPowerBIO platform is set to facilitate the gathering of SME profiles and involve their supporting clusters to assess their investment readiness and ultimately define with them a business support roadmap tailored to their particular needs.

Task 2.1 main objective is to analyse the features that MPowerBIO Platform should provide to its users and turn this into specifications for the developers (submitted as deliverable D2.1 Specifications for the MPowerBIO digital tools) and to design it. As presented in the DoA, the Platform has three main features:

- MPowerBIO website to provide an online visibility to the project
- Digital tools allowing SMEs/projects to apply and SME clusters to assess the applying SMEs investment readiness level (IRL), as well as recommend services from the Business Support Programme to help them improve their investment readiness.
- An e-learning tool that will host all the online courses developed by MPowerBIO Project.

The task leader Tech Tour Global worked with Food & Bio Cluster Denmark and the MPowerBIO project consortium members to define the structure and content of the project website and its design using a content management system. With input from WP1, the task leader also defined the requirements for the digital toolbox supporting the different processes and of the e-learning tool that will host the material prepared for the capacity building programme for SME clusters and the business support programme for SMEs. These specifications were submitted in the deliverable D2.1. The current deliverable D2.4 MPowerBIO Digital Platform is about a Website. The website itself is available publicly at the following URL: <https://MPowerBIO.eu/> and this deliverable will provide a description and screenshots of the main functionalities.

Executive Summary

The current document is produced as deliverable D2.4 MPowerBIO Digital Tools in the framework of the MPowerBIO project which is funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 887501.

While the MPowerBIO Digital tools are available publicly online at the following web address <https://MPowerBIO.eu/>, this document provides a description of the main functionalities and screenshots of the completed MPowerBIO platform, designed in accordance with the specifications of the deliverable D2.1 MPowerBIO digital toolbox. As described in the specifications the MPowerBIO platform is based on a customized digital system used in other projects (InvestHorizon). The platform supports data collection from SMEs and Clusters and allows clusters to assess the investment readiness level of the applying SMEs. The platform also facilitates the hosting of online training material developed by the consortium partners to SMEs and provides SME clusters, industry experts and coaches tools to better support their SMEs and improve their investor readiness.

In this context, MPowerBIO project consortium has designed and deployed the platform based on the afore-mentioned specifications, with three main components deployed and ready to be used:

- A MPowerBIO project website
- An SME application and Investment Readiness Level (IRL) assessment tool
- An e-learning tool that will host training materials for both SME clusters (Capacity Building Programme) and SMEs (Business Support Programme)

1. Main characteristics of the MPowerBIO digital tools

1.1 Operational procedures

The main users of the platform are SMEs, Clusters, Industry experts and investors. Each targeted user can access the following:

The entrepreneurs can go on the website and see information about MPowerBIO, see the application window, read about the key services provided, see a list of supporting partners, access relevant industry news, see the events calendar once it is posted and other useful resources. SMEs are also able to fill in a profile and complete a self-assessment investment readiness level form. They will also be able to go through recommended on-line trainings which will boost their investment readiness.

Backing up clusters, industry experts and investors will be part of the value delivery chain assessing investment readiness levels of applying SMEs, recommending the SMEs to participate in specific training activities from the Business Support Programme put in place by MPowerBIO and attending workshops and events together with selected SMEs. By participating in the support activities provided to the SMEs, the supporting clusters will build their own capacity and be empowered to better support their SMEs.

Backoffice users can create and upload courses, create events, collect applications and track the full process thanks to the functionalities provided by the MPowerBIO platform.

1.2 Technologies used for creation of the platform

The MPowerBIO platform is using several existing components such as:

- Drupal as content management system
- AWS for the hosting of the different components
- Tech Tour platform for the Backoffice
- Cognito forms for the applications and evaluations
- Integromat to automate the connection between the different components
- Google forms for the process tracking
- Moodle for the online courses
- Jira for user feedback collector

The figure below provides the high level architecture of the platform.

Figure 1-MPowerBIO Platform architecture

1.3 Resources

A download section for all the communication materials as well as project reports and deliverables will be available on the MPowerBIO website.

1.4 Privacy policy

The MPowerBIO website has a separate page related to the privacy and cookie policy where users can find information on the data protection notice and the cookies.

2. Main Pages of the MPowerBIO website

2.1 Site map

The figure below provides an overview of the MPowerBIO website map.

Figure 2-MPowerBIO website map

2.2 Website structure

The MPowerBIO website follows a structure that is lean, consistent, and aligned with the main goals of the project in order to help clusters and SMEs to build set of key skills and gain knowledge and provide opportunities to work together over a number of planned activities.

At this stage the MPowerBIO website features the pages:

Main Menu

- About
 - Partners
 - Advisory Board
- Services
- News
- Contact
- Apply Now
 - Application form

Footer

- Privacy & Cookies policy
- Terms & Conditions
- Contact

After a pilot of the below modules, we intend to roll out the following pages of the MPowerBIO website in addition to the above already existing ones:

Main Menu

- [Courses](#)
- [Events](#)
- [Resources](#)

Footer

- [FAQ](#)

With the proposed structure we would like to ensure that users of the website will be able to access the information they need easily and will not have to go one or two levels deeper to get a requested page. This is why we decided to stay away from submenus.

Home

The homepage offers references to what the project is about, motivation why target audience should be interested, what is the value proposition and who is behind the project.

There is a leading slider to host recent announcements and developments with the program and to keep visitors informed and updated. It allows the consortium to communicate key messages and push visitors to action.

The below screenshots provide an idea about the structure and content of the MPowerBIO project website.

Figure 3-Front page part one

What is MPowerBIO

MPowerBIO will empower 90 clusters within the bio-based industry across Europe to be better equipped to help SMEs overcome the challenge of finding sufficient investment to get from idea to business. By developing an online platform with digital tools our goal is to get 250 SMEs one step closer to capturing investment.

Why participate

SMEs

- Get tools to enhance your investment readiness
- Get in touch with investors regionally and internationally
- Get concrete advice on your business strategy and pitch

Clusters

- Be better equipped to help your SME members become ready for investment
- You can add a new service to your portfolio which your members can benefit from – or improve the existing service
- Upgrade the skills of your secretariat

Investors

- Get in touch with SMEs that can present attractive business plans ready for investment
- One point of entry to over 250 SMEs with high-growth potential within the bio-based industry
- Get a “greener” investment profile

Figure 4-Front page part two

How does it work?

Figure 5-Front page part three

Key services

Capacity building programme

Increase your success rate in helping your SME members gain access to funding. The capacity building programme is designed to support you in assessing the challenges of gaining access to funding and to be able to deliver better advice and services for your SME members.

[Read More](#)

Business support programme

Let's make your business ready for investment. Identify your challenges and weaknesses and receive tailored support to improve your chances to capture investments for your bio-based industry projects. Discover how we can help you and your business succeed.

[Read More](#)

Events

Participate in free regional training events and EU wide networking events to boost your investment readiness and growth potential and connect with investors and potential partners.

[Read More](#)

Figure 6-Front page part four

Partners

Get in touch

We'd love to have your feedback and answer your questions

[Contact us](#)

[Privacy & Cookies Policy](#) [Terms and Conditions](#) [Contact](#)

2020 MPowerBIO All rights reserved

This project has received funding from the Bio Based Industries Joint Undertaking (JU) under grant agreement No 887501. The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and the Bio Based Industries Consortium. This output reflects only the author's view and the JU cannot be held responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Figure 7-Front page part five

About

About page provides detailed explanation of the project, its goals and objectives and how we plan to accomplish them.

Additionally the users can get more information about the partners involved in the project and the expert group of the MPowerBIO Advisory board.

Home > About

About

MPowerBIO empowers Clusters to bring SMEs across the financial valley of death

Many SMEs experience that even though they have a good idea or a good product, they cannot get an investor. They need to be able to pitch their idea perfectly, have a strong business plan, a clear strategy, a well-defined customer base, etc. to attract investors.

European clusters need to be better suited to help small and medium sized enterprises (SMEs) overcome the valley of death i.e. the difficult task of finding sufficient investment to get from idea to business. This is the main focus of the MPowerBIO project.

In the MPowerBIO project 10 training the trainers' events will be arranged for a total of 90 clusters across the bioeconomy, covering most of Europe. The events are set up to help clusters understand how SMEs can obtain capital and grow.

Our goals and objectives

Figure 8-About view page part one

How will we reach the goals?

01 Identify investment challenges

The MPowerBIO project will obtain feedback from clusters, SMEs and investors on the concrete challenges they have regarding investments. From these experiences, an online platform will be set up containing digital tools for evaluating investment readiness.

02 Train clusters and support SMEs

Online training modules and regional trainers' events will be organised to build the capacity of clusters to train their SME members and give them the best possibilities for preparing and presenting high quality projects to investors.

03 Pitching in front of investors

The best SME projects from these events will be selected by investors, and invited to one of two European finals, which are based on the European Bioeconomy Venture Forum model, run by several of the consortium members. At the final, the selected companies will present their ideas to a panel of investors and experts from large organisations and venture funds in Europe, with the aim of attracting capital to grow and develop their business.

A total of 72 high-quality, screened and investment-ready SME are expected to pitch at the two final events. The project will screen and support 250 SMEs towards this goal.

Figure 9-About view page part two

Partners

Food & Bio Cluster Denmark

Food & Bio Cluster Denmark is a non-profit nationwide cluster organization for f

Tech Tour

TechTour brings together active corporates and investors in Europe with promising entrepreneurs.

CLIB Cluster

CLIB is an international open innovation cluster for bioeconomy with a focus on industrial biotechnology.

Fundacion Corporacion Tecnologica de Andalucia

Technological Corporation of Andalusia (CTA) is a private foundation that was born from a public-private partnership.

Consorzio Italbiotec

The Consorzio Italbiotec is the leading Italian non-profit organisation on biotechnology ecosystem.

FoodScale Hub

Foodscale Hub helps food start-ups accelerate their growth, open to new markets and find investors.

EIT Food

EIT Food is Europe's leading food innovation initiative, working to make the food system more sustainable, healthy and trusted.

Irish Bioeconomy Foundation

The Irish Bioeconomy Foundation is Ireland's national bioeconomy association and innovation cluster.

Q-Plan International Advisors PC

Q-PLAN is an innovation and management consulting company that has its focus on provision of business and innovation support services.

Sustainable Innovations

Sustainable Innovations is a Spanish consultancy that provides services to a wide range of sectors.

[See more](#)

Figure 10-About view page part three

Advisory board

See more

MPowerBIO Privacy & Cookies Policy Terms and Conditions Contact

2020 MPowerBIO All rights reserved

This project has received funding from the Bio Based Industries Joint Undertaking (JU) under grant agreement No 887501. The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and the Bio Based Industries Consortium. This output reflects only the author's view and the JU cannot be held responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

BBI JU Bio-based Industries Consortium Horizon 2020 European Union Funding for Research & Innovation

Figure 11-About view page part four

Services

The services page gives information about what services the MPowerBIO project provides, for who and how.

Home > Services

Services

Whether you are a SME or a cluster, we offer a set of tailored services that have been carefully selected to meet your needs in relation to improving your investment readiness for your bio-based industry projects. Click below to discover how we can help you succeed.

I am

SME

Cluster

Figure 12-Services page part one

Services for SMEs

Business support programme

Ready to be ready? The Business Support Program includes services selected to meet the needs of the participants such as:

Bioeconomy Bootcamps <p>Through bioeconomy bootcamps SMEs can upgrade their skills by participating in pitching training sessions and interactive workshops. Read More</p>			
--	---	---	---

How do we do it?

01 Self-assessment

Each interested SME will fill in a profile and fill in a customised self-assessment questionnaire that helps assessing its investment readiness.

02 Assessment by clusters

Following the self-assessment made by the SME itself, an assessment will be done by the associated cluster to which the SME is related, and another assessment will be made by a second cluster (or an appointed expert)

03 Action plan

Finally, the two clusters will define together with the SME, based on the three assessments, an action plan with services to be taken by the SME to improve its investor readiness.

Figure 13-Services page part two

I am

Services for Clusters

Capacity building programme

MPowerBIO aims to empower clusters to help their SMEs gain access to funding. To achieve this, we will prepare and deploy a capacity building programme. It will be designed to address the most important skills for clusters with respect to effectively engaging with investors and relevant financial instruments, as well as training their SMEs members to improve their investment readiness and successfully pitch their projects to investors.

During the first months of the project, MPowerBIO partners will screen available documentation, analyse the needs and requirements of financial instruments and investors, and prepare an online survey to map the skills and skill gaps of SME clusters.

Based on our findings, and together with a co-creation workshop, we will develop a targeted capacity building programme which will be made available online. Cluster representatives can either follow the programme at their own pace or take advantage of the regional workshops and online events.

Check back to see the upcoming work and results.

Learn more about the benefits of [joining in as an associated cluster](#).

Figure 14-Services page part three

News

The news page provides relevant information about the MPowerBIO Project, press releases and articles.

Home > News

News

One step closer to the design of a capacity building and business support programme
On 29 October MPowerBIO hosted an online co-creation workshop, where the participants provided val
Mon, 11/02/2020 - 12:29

Help SMEs capture investment: Make your mark on the design of MPowerBIO's capacity building and business support programme
Are you an investor, an expert within the bio based industry or a representative from an SME or a
Tue, 10/13/2020 - 12:29

MPowerBIO represented at AseBio Investor Day 2020
On 28 September Iakovos Delioglani from the partner organisation Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL presented p
Tue, 09/29/2020 - 12:45

European bioeconomy clusters get new digital tools to help SMEs overcome the valley of death
Press release, 7 May 2020
Thu, 05/07/2020 - 13:31

Figure 15-News page

Contact

Home > Contact

Contact

First Name	Last Name
<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Organization name	Email Address
<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>

Message related to:
- Select -

Message

[Send message](#)

Britt Sandvad
Project coordinator
+45 2040 9679
bs@foodbiocluster.dk

MPowerBIO [Privacy & Cookies Policy](#) [Terms and Conditions](#) [Contact](#)

Figure 16-Contact page

3.2.4 Apply now

We decided to show the Apply now page as a button which allows interested SMEs and clusters to access the application from. The application forms are described in the next section.

3. Application and assessment tool

The next set of features provided by the MPowerBIO platform facilitates the application process: application for clusters and application for SMEs.

3.1 Cluster Application

This part of the website enables the engagement of associated clusters who will be involved in the delivery of MPowerBIO services to applying SMEs. The clusters can register and engage through the platform by filling out information about their organisations; their profiles are to be enlisted and will have access to company profiles as well as to use the MPowerBIO services for clusters and SMEs.

Associated Cluster Form

Cluster Name *	Website *
<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Contact Person Name *	
First <input type="text"/>	Last <input type="text"/>
Contact Person Email *	Contact Person Phone *
<input type="text"/>	+34 123456 <input type="text"/>
Are you based in EU or Associated Country? *	Country *
<input checked="" type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No	<input type="text" value="Please specify which country"/>
Are you active in the bioeconomy field? *	Number of SMEs within your cluster *
<input checked="" type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No	<input type="text" value="Please specify how many SMEs do you have"/>
Activityi *	
<input type="text" value="Please tell us more about your activities (max 500 symbols)"/>	
Networks with other stakeholders of the bioeconomy area	
<input type="text" value="Please tell us more about your organization's network (max 500 symbols)"/>	
<input type="submit" value="Submit"/>	

3.2 SMEs Application

The companies will apply for MPowerBIO services by filling in an online form.

The first part of the application is about eligibility of the applicant:

- Country of HQ: from a H2020 or Associated Country
- Operating in biobased industry sector or market, in accordance with the European Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform (<https://circulareconomy.europa.eu/platform/en/knowledge>)
- Being a member of a cluster
- Statement about commitment to actively take part in the programme if selected

If eligible, the company continues with the application, providing information about five dimensions of their business:

1. product/technology outline
2. business/market description
3. management description including a short CV of the CEO
4. competitiveness description
5. financials, investment need and proposition with a slide deck towards potential investors

The company is then screened by an expert who is nominated by the consortium or an associated cluster or MPowerBIO consortium. This screening is simply to check if the applicant could be of any interest to investors.

The screening of the applications will serve as a ground to invite the company to the next step consisting of conducting a self-assessment and an assessment by experts from the consortium and the associated clusters of its Investment Readiness Level described in the next section.

Application for Business Support Services

First Name *
Last Name *

Code *
Phone *
Email *

Are You Part of a Bio-based Cluster *
 Yes No

Gender
 Female Male Prefer not to answer

Note: If you responded with "No" your application will be valid only when you join a cluster.

I agree to the Terms and Conditions

Figure 18-Application page part one

MPOWERBIO Application

[Management Team](#)
[Eligibility Checklist](#)
[Company Details](#)
[Application Details](#)

Your role in applying company *
Job Title *

Short Bio
 Briefly describe your experience (max 500 characters)

Upload CV of the CEO
 or drag files here.

Profile Picture of the CEO
 or drag files here.

Management Team

Figure 19-Application page part two

MPowerBIO Application

Management Team

Eligibility Checklist

Company Details

Application Details

Eligibility Self-Check

This checklist will help you define whether you are eligible for MPowerBIO Business Services. Check our [FAQ](#) section for more info.

SME Country *

Select

Yes No

SME is based in a [EU Member State](#) and [Horizon 2020 associated countries](#).

SME commitment

The executive director commits to take part in the accelerator recommended track services

Select

Yes No

Cluster Name *

Select

Yes No

Presentation

Add a pitch deck to your application.

Upload Presentation or Pitch Deck

or drag files here.

[Download a template](#)

Max file size 20MB

Figure 20-Application page part three

MpowerBIO Application

Management Team

Eligibility Checklist

Company Details

Application Details

Company Details

Company Logo

Upload

or drag files here.

Company Name *

Company Summary

Briefly describe your organisation (max. 500 characters)

Key Bioeconomy Area *

- Production Consumption Waste Management

- Secondary Raw Materials Innovation and Investments

Bioeconomy Sectors *

- Adhesives, coatings Agriculture Aquaculture
- B2B Services Bio-based materials and solutions for housing and urban development Bio-based materials for electronics and ICT
- Bio-based products for automotive industry Biofuels Business incubators, startups
- Circular design Chemical Management Circular Action for climate neutrality
- Clothing industry Construction, buildings and infrastructure

Figure 21-Application page part four

<input type="checkbox"/> Bio-based products for automotive industry	<input type="checkbox"/> Biofuels	<input type="checkbox"/> Business incubators, startups
<input type="checkbox"/> Circular design	<input type="checkbox"/> Chemical Management	<input type="checkbox"/> Circular Action for climate neutrality
<input type="checkbox"/> Corporate procurement	<input type="checkbox"/> Clothing industry	<input type="checkbox"/> Construction, buildings and infrastructure
<input type="checkbox"/> Digital solutions for bio-based industries	<input type="checkbox"/> Cosmetics and personal care	<input type="checkbox"/> Crop protection, fertilisers
<input type="checkbox"/> Feed	<input type="checkbox"/> Economic instruments	<input type="checkbox"/> Education and skills
<input type="checkbox"/> Food, water and nutrients	<input type="checkbox"/> Empowering Consumers	<input type="checkbox"/> Energy and waste- to- energy
<input type="checkbox"/> Governance	<input type="checkbox"/> Fertilisers	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibers
<input type="checkbox"/> Innovation and investment	<input type="checkbox"/> Forestry	<input type="checkbox"/> Furniture
<input type="checkbox"/> Mobility and transport	<input type="checkbox"/> Industrial symbiosis	<input type="checkbox"/> Industrial techniques
<input type="checkbox"/> Pharmaceuticals	<input type="checkbox"/> Machinery and Equipment	<input type="checkbox"/> Measuring circularity
<input type="checkbox"/> Public services	<input type="checkbox"/> Packaging	<input type="checkbox"/> Personal and household goods
<input type="checkbox"/> Recycling	<input type="checkbox"/> Plastics, Polymers and Rubber	<input type="checkbox"/> Public procurement
<input type="checkbox"/> Research	<input type="checkbox"/> Pulp and Paper Industry (PPI)	<input type="checkbox"/> Recover, Regenerative economy
<input type="checkbox"/> Social impact	<input type="checkbox"/> Refineries	<input type="checkbox"/> Repair, Refurbishment, Remanufacture, Repurpose
	<input type="checkbox"/> Retail	<input type="checkbox"/> Re-think, Reduce, Reuse
	<input type="checkbox"/> Soils, soil improvement and restoration	<input type="checkbox"/> Textiles, apparel and leather
		<input type="checkbox"/> Waste management & Secondary Raw Materials
<input type="checkbox"/> Water	<input type="checkbox"/> Other	

Figure 22-Application page part six

City * <input type="text"/>	Country * Afghanistan	
Turnover <input type="text" value="Select from the list"/>	Number of employees <input type="text" value="Select from the list"/>	Founded <input type="text" value="Year"/>
Twitter <input type="text" value="https://twitter.com/"/>	Website <input type="text" value="https://www.OrganisationWebsite.com"/>	
Facebook <input type="text" value="https://www.facebook.com/"/>	LinkedIn <input type="text"/>	
SME Interest <input type="text" value="What are you looking for"/>		
Organisation Completeness % 55,56		
<input type="button" value="Back"/>	<input type="button" value="Next"/>	<input type="button" value="Save"/>

Figure 23-Application page part seven

MPowerBIO Application

Management Team

Eligibility Checklist

Company Details

Application Details

Application Details

Product & Technology

Tell us more about your product (max 1000 characters)

Market & Business Potential

Tell us more about what your market looks like (max 1000 characters)

Competitive Position

Tell us more about how you plan to outrun your competitors (max 1000 characters)

Figure 24-Application page part eight

Financials and Investment Proposition

Investor 1

Investor (Fund) Name	Year of Investment	Percentage
<input type="text"/>	<input type="text" value="Year"/>	<input type="text" value="%"/>
Investment Amount (EUR)	Investment Type	
<input type="text"/>	<input type="text" value="Select from the list"/>	
Investor's Contact Name	Investor's Email	
<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	

+ Add Investor

Key financials 1

Year	Revenue (EUR)	Net Income (EUR)
<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Gross Margin (%)	Operating Expenses (EUR)	Operating Margin (EUR)
<input type="text" value="%"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Head count	COGS (EUR)	EBIT (EUR)
<input type="text" value="Number of people"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>

+ Add Key financials

I agree that information to seen by experts and clusters within the network of MPowerBIO.

Application details completeness %
0,00

Back **Submit** **Save**

Figure 25-Application page part nine

3.3 SMEs Self-assessment of Investment Readiness Level

After completing the first step in the application process, the company is screened by an expert from the consortium or from an associated cluster. This screening simply checks if the applicant could be of any interest to investors and gives greenlight to the company to proceed to the next step where more information is required to assess its Investment Readiness Level.

To this end, companies with potential will be invited to undertake a self-assessment of their Investment Readiness Level. After the company fills in its own self-assessment form, an expert from the consortium or from an associated cluster will fill a similar assessment form (giving his own opinion

and motivations) and compare with the company view and generate a baseline investment readiness score based on 5 intrinsic readiness and 2 presentational readiness dimensions:

- Intrinsic readiness:

1. Management
2. Product
3. Business/Market
4. Competition
5. Financials

- Presentation Readiness:

6. Summary Quality
7. Pitch quality

The self-assessment and expert assessment exercise allow the experts to identify strengths and weaknesses of the applying companies and recommend specific services from the MPowerBIO Business Support Programme to the applicant to improve its investment readiness (Service Action Plan).

The below screenshots give an idea about the self-assessments of Investment Readiness Level of companies.

Organisation name *

Email *

1. Management

The Entrepreneur/CEO is knowledgeable, experienced and motivated

Score *

Score (1-10)

The Team (CTO/CSO, CFO, COO/Production, Sales, HR) is complete, knowledgeable, experienced, motivated and diverse

Score (1-10)

The Board functions well with regular well prepared meetings and calls with experienced shareholder and independent representatives

Score (1-10)

Sub Total Strengths & Weaknesses MANAGEMENT (%)

Sub Total SW

0,00

The HR and Leadership Gaps (Human Resources vs. Needs) are identified for Leadership (CEO, ...) and Staff with skills, culture and process definition

Score (1-10)

An HR Plan is in place to strengthen Leadership and also to scale Staff with processes for recruitment, training, development and incentives

Score (1-10)

Sub Total Opportunities & Threats MANAGEMENT (%)

Sub Total OT

0,00

Figure 26-Self-Assessment part one

2. Product

There is a prototype Product with a defined Value Proposition fitting a specific Pain/Problem of a targeted group of customers	Score * Score (1-10)
There is Validation with Target customers and of the scalability of the Production	Score (1-10)
There is Proprietary Knowledge and an advanced research base carried by a team and partnerships and, if possible, protected (patents)	Score (1-10)
Sub Total Strengths & Weaknesses PRODUCT (%)	Sub Total SW 0,00
There is a Product Development Roadmap with a proven capability and team to manage and steer it	Score (1-10)
There are Partnerships in place to accelerate the Development and to increase or optimise the Production/Service capacity	Score (1-10)
Sub Total Opportunities & Threats PRODUCT (%)	Sub Total OT 0,00

Figure 27-Self-Assessment part two

3. Business

The Targeted Market of customers is defined and sizeable, adressable and growing. There are reports, data and insights to prove it	Score * Score (1-10)
The Business Model and Pricing Strategy is sound and based on market analysis and early/pilot customer validation	Score (1-10)
The Sales Model and distribution channels have been defined and are tested or in progress with initial customers and a potential list	Score (1-10)
Sub Total Strengths & Weaknesses BUSINESS (%)	0,00
The Revenues are made Scalable as production, sales, delivery and services have been productised and standardised	Score (1-10)
Potential Strategic Partnerships have been identified and assessed to adress new geographies, sectors and adjacent customer needs	Score (1-10)
Sub Total Opportunities & Threats BUSINESS (%)	Sub Total OT 0,00

Figure 28-Self-Assessment part three

4. Competition

The **Main Competitors** today and going forward are identified, tracked and assessed also in their product and market strategy

Score *

Score (1-10)

The **Differentiation** of the product and market position vs. the Competitors is outlined and compelling ("unfair" competitive advantage)

Score (1-10)

The **Main Customers** are **Loyal** or can be solid repeat sales and with increasing account revenues

Score (1-10)

Sub Total Strengths & Weaknesses COMPETITION (%)

SubTotalSW

0,00

Strategic Alliances are or can be in place which provide or lock in customer access or access to key resources

Score (1-10)

The **Competitive Strategy** includes mergers and acquisition options as well as hiring talented development or sales teams away

Score (1-10)

Sub Total Opportunities & Threats COMPETITION (%)

Sub Total OT

0,00

Figure 29-Self-Assessment part four

5. Investment

The **Cash (Flow) Position** is strong and tightly managed, considering even potential delays in the planned revenues or Series A fund-raising

Score *

Score (1-10)

The past and future 3 to 5 years **Financials** are available. Accounting, Payments, Budgeting and Forecasting are kept (monthly) and audited.

Score (1-10)

The Series A **Investment Need** and use of funding, terms and valuation are specified & realistic. Corporate, shareholding, tax and legals are clean.

Score (1-10)

Sub Total Strengths & Weaknesses INVESTMENT (%)

Sub Total SW

0,00

There is a solid **Plan B** if the Series A fund raising is not raised or only in part. Timely contingencies and alternatives are specified.

Score (1-10)

Initial commitments of investors are in place seeking other lead or co-investors alongside them and the entrepreneurial shareholders

Score (1-10)

Sub Total Opportunities & Threats INVESTMENT (%)

Sub Total OT

0,00

Figure 30-Self-Assessment part five

6. Communications

The Summary Profile and Slide Deck are complete, relevant, accurate, coherent, enticing and well written and presented.	Score * Score (1-10)
The Business Plan as well as relevant Due Diligence materials are available and of high standard	Score (1-10)
The Corporate and Commercial Communications including website, video, online materials and social media activities are informative and attractive	Score (1-10)
Sub Total Strengths & Weaknesses INVESTMENT (%) Sub Total SW 0,00	
The CEO/entrepreneur is viewed as an industry thought leader, energetic communicator and charismatic team leader	Score (1-10)
The Public Relations Strategy, Plan and Resources provide industry recognition, press visibility, awards and community good citizenship	Score (1-10)
Sub Total Opportunities & Threats INVESTMENT (%) Sub Total OT 0,00	

Figure 31-Self-Assessment part six

Self-Assessment DEMO

If you agree with the scores, click Submit. Otherwise go back and review your answers.

Strengths and Weaknesses			
MANAGEMENT (%)	10,00	COMPETITION (%)	10,00
PRODUCT (%)	10,00	INVESTMENT (%)	10,00
BUSINESS (%)	10,00	COMMUNICATIONS (%)	10,00

Opportunities and Threats			
MANAGEMENT (%)	10,00	COMPETITION (%)	10,00
PRODUCT (%)	10,00	INVESTMENT (%)	10,00
BUSINESS (%)	10,00	COMMUNICATIONS (%)	10,00

Back

Submit

Figure 32-Self-Assessment part seven

3.4 Assessment by experts

Once applicants have undertaken their own self-assessment, experts from associated clusters or from the consortium will be appointed to assess them based on the profile and self-assessment information provided, particularly on their management experience, product, business model, competitive advantages, investment readiness and communication channels.

The screenshots below give an idea about the expert assessment process.

Evaluator's information

First name *	Last name *
<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Organisation *	Your work email *
<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>

Application ID *	Applicant `s organisation *	Applicant `s Email *
<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>

1. Management

The Entrepreneur/CEO is knowledgeable, experienced and motivated	Score *
	<input type="text" value="Score (1-10)"/>
The Team (CTO/CSO, CFO, COO/Production, Sales, HR) is complete, knowledgeable, experienced, motivated and diverse	Score (1-10)
	<input type="text" value="Score (1-10)"/>
The Board functions well with regular well prepared meetings and calls with experienced shareholder and independent representatives	Score (1-10)
	<input type="text" value="Score (1-10)"/>
Sub Total Strengths & Weaknesses MANAGEMENT (%)	Sub Total SW
	0,00

Please motivate your score *

Figure 33-Expert Assessment part one

2. Product

There is a prototype **Product with a defined Value Proposition** fitting a specific Pain/Problem of a targeted group of customers

Score *

Score (1-10)

There is **Validation with Target customers** and of the scalability of the Production

Score (1-10)

There is **Proprietary Knowledge** and an advanced research base carried by a team and partnerships and, if possible, protected (patents)

Score (1-10)

Sub Total Strengths & Weaknesses PRODUCT (%) **Sub Total SW**
0,00

Please motivate your score *

3. Business

The **Targeted Market** of customers is defined and sizeable, adressable and growing. There are reports, data and insights to prove it

Score *

Score (1-10)

The **Business Model and Pricing Strategy** is sound and based on market analysis and early/pilot customer validation

Score (1-10)

The **Sales Model** and distribution channels have been defined and are tested or in progress with initial customers and a potential list

Score (1-10)

Sub Total Strengths & Weaknesses BUSINESS (%) 0,00

Please motivate your score *

Figure 34-Expert Assessment part two

4. Competition

The **Main Competitors** today and going forward are identified, tracked and assessed also in their product and market strategy

Score *

Score (1-10)

The **Differentiation** of the product and market position vs. the Competitors is outlined and compelling ("unfair" competitive advantage)

Score (1-10)

The **Main Customers** are **Loyal** or can be solid repeat sales and with increasing account revenues

Score (1-10)

Sub Total Strengths & Weaknesses COMPETITION (%)

SubTotalSW

0,00

Please motivate your score *

5. Investment

The **Cash (Flow) Position** is strong and tightly managed, considering even potential delays in the planned revenues or Series A fund-raising

Score *

Score (1-10)

The past and future 3 to 5 years **Financials** are available and are realistic.

Score (1-10)

The Series A **Investment Need** and use of funding are specified and realistic.

Score (1-10)

Sub Total Strengths & Weaknesses INVESTMENT (%)

Sub Total SW

0,00

Please motivate your score *

Figure 35-Expert Assessment part three

6. Communications

The **Summary Profile and Slide Deck** are complete, relevant, accurate, coherent, enticing and well written and presented.

Score *

Score (1-10)

The **unique value proposition** is convincingly described and communicated.

Score (1-10)

The **Corporate and Commercial Communications** including website, video, online materials and social media activities are informative and attractive.

Score (1-10)

Sub Total Strengths & Weaknesses INVESTMENT (%)

Sub Total SW

0,00

Please motivate your score *

Figure 36-Expert Assessment part four

3.3. Generating a Service Action Plan

The self-assessment and expert assessment processes help generating a Service Action Plan for each applicant, including a list of MPowerBIO services recommended to the applicant in order to improve its investment readiness.

The screenshot below gives an idea about the Service Action Plan.

Accelerator Action Plan

Trust Group Programme Bootcamps Pitching & e-Pitching Webinars & Online Courses

Name of the Trust Group

App ID * Applicant's email *
 ID Email of applicant

Company Lead Account Coach (LAC):
 Company Name Name and Surname

Entrepreneur Member (EM): Analyst Account Coach (AAC):
 Name and Surname Name and Surname

Entrepreneur Second Member(ESM) Supporting Investor Member (SIM):
 Name and Surname Name and Surname

Accelerator Trust Group Programme

Confirmation of Supporting Investor Signature of Non-Disclosure Agreement - Entrepreneur
 No No

Participation in Online Trust Group Signature of Non-Disclosure Agreement - Supporting Investor
 No No

1 / 4

Figure 37-Generating a Service Action Plan

4. E-learning tool

At the moment the e-learning tool has been integrated with the MPowerBIO platform. Moodle tool is installed and functional. However, the content that needs to be uploaded and used to build capacity of the associated clusters and train the SMEs to develop their business capacity is still being developed by the consortium partners and will be available at a later stage. The e-learning module is therefore still not made public and will be publicly accessible at later stage.

5. Future steps

Next steps are to include on the website the following:

- Digital tools: Training materials for use by clusters and SMEs to facilitate the gathering of SMEs profiles, assess their investment readiness level and identify their strengths and weaknesses. In addition, guides will be available for SME clusters on how to help their SMEs

- **Courses:** the courses produced by the consortium partners will be uploaded on the e-learning tool and the tool will be activated when some relevant material is available.
- **Events:** A calendar showing all upcoming events related to the MPowerBIO project. The calendar is divided into different categories, so it is easy to find the type of event you are looking for. This requires that the events to be organised by MPowerBIO are defined and planned.
- **Resources:** A download section for all the communication materials as well as project report deliverables. The section will be continuously fed when such material is available.